

Safe ground water : I, contamination of ground water of Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India by nitrate, sulfates and alkalinity

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Abstract : Nitrate is a problem in drinking water due to its harmful biological effects. High concentrations of nitrate are reported to cause methemoglobinemia, and have been established as a risk factor in developing gastric and intestinal cancer. Nitrate contamination of ground water has become a major challenge to the environmentalist, especially in the developing countries. The city of Varanasi withdraws a significant amount of drinking water from ground water sources. A large section of population in semi urban and rural areas of the district depends on ground water for drinking purpose. The present study was intended to identify the locations affected by nitrate contamination in ground water around Varanasi city. Both open wells (30 nos) and tube wells (15 nos) have been considered as sources supplying drinking water to the population. In addition to nitrates, the concentration of sulphates and alkalinity was specifically determined in the samples. Other quality parameters of concerns included in this study are pH, temperature, total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, chloride, dissolved oxygen (DO).

Keywords : Nitrate contamination, ground water, BIS, Varanasi.

Introduction

Varanasi, also commonly known as *Benares* or *Banaras* and *Kashi* (in Hindi), is a city situated on the banks of the River Ganges in the Indian state of Uttar Pradesh, regarded as holy city by Hindus, Buddhists, and Jains. The district Varanasi is located in south-west portion of Uttar Pradesh having geographical coordinates 82°15' to 83°30' East longitude and 24°35' to 25°30' North latitude. The geographical area of the district is 1535 sq. km. Varanasi district forms part of central Ganga plain physiographically the district can be divided into two physical regions, i.e. the northern alluvial plain and the southern plateau area. Varanasi has a humid subtropical climate with high variation between summer and winter temperatures¹.

In many parts of the world, ground water is only source of drinking water in rural communities and urban areas. Ground water serves as the source of drinking water for a large population in India. More than 95% of the rural population and about 30 to 40% of urban population in India depend on ground water for their domestic requirement. Ground water is a major source of urban and rural

society of Varanasi for drinking purpose. The modern civilization, industrialization, urbanization and increase in population have lead to fast degradation of our ground water quality². Nitrate is possibly the most widespread ground water contaminant in the world, causing a serious problem to human health and eutrophication^{3,4}. High concentrations of nitrate has been linked to agricultural activities due to the use of nitrogenous fertilizers. Elevated nitrate levels in ground water mainly result from human and animal wastes, and excessive use of nitrogenous fertilizers. The regions where agricultural activities are highly intensive, nitrate concentrations in ground water are usually above the permissible level for nitrate in drinking water. Excessive use of chemicals and fertilizers increases the risk of ground water contamination^{5,6}. Nitrate in ground water comes from many sources such as nitrogen fertilizers, animal wastes, municipal wastes, landfills, septic tanks, soil organic matters⁷ and discharge of domestic and industrial wastewater^{5,6}. Studies in the last few years have found that nitrate concentrations in some urban aquifers are similar or even higher to those

in their surrounding agricultural areas⁸.

This is also true for the various forms of nitrogen (oxidized and reduced forms) that are present in many possible recharge sources of urban aquifers. They include sewage mains leakage, septic tanks, industrial spillages, contaminated land, landfills, river or channel infiltration, fertilizers used in gardens, house building, storm water and direct recharge. Because of the number of nitrogen sources in urban areas, it is not surprising to find elevated nitrogen concentrations in urban aquifers⁹.

In addition to agricultural practices, non-point sources of nitrogen involve precipitation, irrigation with ground-water containing nitrogen and dry deposition¹⁰ and the major point sources include septic tanks and dairy lagoons.

Excess of nitrate in water can cause several problems. The effect of nitrate itself is called primary toxicity. Its high intake in drinking water causes abdominal pain, diarrhea, vomiting, hypertension, increased infant mortality, central nervous systems defects, birth defects, diabetes, spontaneous abortions, respiratory tract infections and changes to the immune system. Secondary toxicity of nitrate is due to microbially reduced reactive nitrite ion in the intestine. It has been implicated in methemoglobi-

nemia, especially in infants of age under 6 months¹¹.

World Health Organization (WHO)¹² has given a guideline value of nitrate for drinking water is 50 mg NO₃⁻/L. However, in India current maximum permissible concentration of nitrate in drinking water prescribed by Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS)¹³ is 45 mg NO₃⁻/L. Setting standards for a drinking water contaminant is a very difficult and may be influenced by economic, political and social issues, in addition to scientific considerations. Because, data related effects of chemicals on human health through drinking water intake are limited, and scientists have difficulty predicting the effects of drinking small amounts of chemicals for many years¹⁴. The values of the parameters namely pH, temperature, total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, sulfates, alkalinity, chloride, dissolved oxygen (DO) in the water samples was also determined and reported.

Results and discussion

Tables 1 and 2 show the results of analyses done on open well and hand pump water samples collected from various sampling points. The following inferences are drawn from the observations and analysis done during the present study.

Table 1. Results of water quality analyses on open well samples

Sl. no.	Site	Temp. (°C)	pH	Turbidity (NTU)	TDS (mg/L)	Alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO ₃)	D.O. (mg/L)	Chloride (mg/L)	Sulfate (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg NO ₃ ⁻ /L)
1.	Nuwan	24	8.2	1.5	500	230	5.6	38	36	22
2.	Barchhawan	25	7.4	1.0	280	220	5.5	89	53	36
3.	Rudauli	26	7.4	1.0	980	207	6.4	59	98	25
4.	Adalpara	27	7.4	1.5	280	207	7.6	56	38	21
5.	Jakhni	25	8.1	0.5	770	337	7.6	82	81	24
6.	Koili	26	7.3	1.5	890	60	6.6	28	31	23
7.	Rajatalab	26	8.0	0.5	940	226	4.7	172	82	27
8.	Mirjamurad	27	7.5	0.5	610	235	5.7	80	74	28
9.	Chitrasenpur	27	7.2	1.0	840	230	5.9	88	63	33
10.	Kapsethi	25	7.3	0.6	480	207	6.3	34	52	24
11.	Harhuan	27	7.3	0.9	1020	490	4.5	128	35	68
12.	Jamalpur	23	7.1	1.2	430	214	5.8	92	91	22
13.	Kuhar	28	7.3	1.7	860	244	5.2	62	52	15
14.	Kharion	24	7.4	1.1	600	285	5.9	80	43	47
15.	Dhabtua	27	7.3	1.0	700	339	5.0	32	76	11
16.	Dabhthua	27	7.3	2.0	480	265	5.1	45	72	27
17.	Kuar	27	8.0	0.4	570	342	6.2	88	42	18

Table-1 (contd.)

18.	Devchandpur	27	8.0	0.5	670	342	4.8	82	34	32
19.	Badagaun	23	7.3	2.5	990	440	4.8	140	75	11
20.	Kundi	26	7.5	5.0	360	250	5.5	32	23	20
21.	Kalikadham	27	7.0	1.7	520	214	5.4	28	58	27
22.	Khardu	26	7.2	1.1	775	245	5.6	100	47	48
23.	Chandmari	25	7.0	0.5	640	305	6.5	60	5	5
24.	Palhipatti	28	7.3	0.6	410	265	5.6	32	7	20
25.	Sindhora	26	7.6	2.0	470	300	6.7	40	10	49
26.	Jewar	26	7.7	1.5	620	305	5.0	50	31	27
27.	Hariadeeh	27	7.6	1.8	710	364	5.1	48	68	33
28.	Narayanpur	28	7.0	2.6	390	360	5.1	122	21	16
29.	Chiraigaon	24	7.6	0.7	133	316	5.2	67	72	50
30.	Jhulhupur	28	7.8	0.3	350	290	5.7	82	30	18

Table 2. Results of water quality analyses on hand pump samples

Sl. no.	Site	Temp. (°C)	pH	Turbidity (NTU)	TDS (mg/L)	Alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO ₃)	D.O. (mg/L)	Chloride (mg/L)	Sulfate (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg NO ₃ ⁻ /L)
1.	Shahansapur	27	7.3	0.5	780	210	5.7	21	8	39
2.	Thatra	27	7.5	0.5	960	265	5.6	81	46	37
3.	Baruka	28	7.2	0.3	840	310	5.2	45	42	16
4.	Karuna	27	7.2	1.0	590	256	5.2	143	83	25
5.	Lohta	24	7.6	0.2	740	307	6.3	33	28	43
6.	Newada	24	7.1	1.2	430	325	6.5	38	8	8
7.	DLW	26	7.3	0.8	325	250	5.8	12	3	2
8.	Shivpur	28	7.2	2.6	700	215	4.7	180	7	47
9.	Bhelupur	29	7.4	0.5	530	260	5.7	74	32	12
10.	Phoolpur	28	7.6	0.4	540	375	7.0	49	28	27
11.	Bashai	28	7.3	12.0	720	314	5.8	89	25	28
12.	Auron	28	7.5	0.1	590	214	6.0	35	89	12
13.	Gurthama Bazar	25	7.2	0.7	425	295	5.2	24	6	12
14.	Sandaha	26	7.7	0.3	480	226	5.3	23	50	40
15.	Lahartara	24	7.3	18.0	450	315	3.0	28	8	3

Water table depth :

It was observed that in most part of the district the water table is below 10 m. The area around village Barchaw in the south and village Dabathua in the north appear to have high ground water tables. These areas may be prone to water logging conditions in post monsoon periods. The water table in Chiraigaon village was found at the lowest depth of 27 m among open wells.

All the 15 hand pumps analyses for ground water quality parameters are at present in use for domestic purposes by the public. Based on the enquiry from the local people, the depths of hand pumps were noted. The varia-

tion of depth of hand pumps across the study area. It is observed that most of the hand pumps draw water from more than 10 m depth. The lowest water table depth was found for Shansapur, Baruka and Karuna, 57, 54 and 50 m respectively.

Dissolved oxygen (D.O.) :

Dissolved oxygen is generally taken as the measure of freshness of water. Both open well and hand pump water samples were analyzed for their D.O. values.

It is observed that baring some parts of the district in south and south-west portion, almost the entire district have open well D.O. between 4-6 mg/L. Observations in

hand pump water samples also indicate similar trend. Some part of the district in north including Adalpura, Jakhni, Mirzamurad and Lohta in central-east portion is having D.O. level in between 6.0 to 7.6 in hand pump waters.

pH :

The pH value is one of the most frequently used water quality parameters. It is observed that all water samples, both from open wells as well as hand pumps are having pH between 7.0 to 8.2. Thus, the pH of water of the district is within permissible limits for domestic purposes.

Alkalinity :

Alkalinity of water affects its taste for human consumption and use in construction purposes. It is observed that baring Koili village in the southern part of the district, water from both open wells as well as tube wells show alkalinity more than 200 mg/L. As per Indian standard, the desirable limit of alkalinity in water for drinking purposes is up to 200 mg/L, because beyond this, it imparts unpleasant taste to water, although in absence of alternate source, the permissible limit has been extended up to 600 mg/L. This indicates that although the water samples are safe from public health point of view in most part of the district, it may create problems of unpleasant taste for some people in the area. As most of the open wells as well as hand pumps draw water from more than 10 m depths, a further investigation seems imperative to ascertain the reasons of this high level of alkalinity being observed in most part of the district.

Turbidity :

Turbidity in water is the physical parameter which determines the public acceptability of water for domestic purposes. These observations indicate that whereas most of the south parts of the district have open well turbidity below 1 NTU, almost whole of northern half of the district give turbidity between 1–5 NTU. The desirable limit for turbidity in water for drinking purpose is 5 NTU. Thus these well waters are well within safe limits of turbidity for human consumptions. The data shows that, there are some parts of the district where the hand pumps give turbidity between 5 to 10 NTU and at one location near village Bashai in south-west part of the district, it reaches to 12 NTU. Above 5 NTU, the consumer acceptability of water decreases, but in case of non availability of alternate source, the permissible limit for turbidity in water

for drinking purposes is 10 NTU¹³. The areas where water turbidity is above 10 NTU may need further investigations to ascertain the reasons for such high levels. The presence of iron may be one of the possibilities.

Total dissolved solids (TDS) :

Dissolve solids is one of the desirable parameters of water for drinking purpose. Obviously, the open wells of eastern part of the district covering around 30–40% of the area have TDS below 500 mg/L, which is the desirable limit for dissolved solids in water for drinking purpose. However, a major part of the district covering almost 60–70% of the total area have TDS more than 500 mg/L and below 2000 mg/L, which is the upper permissible limit in case of non availability of alternate source. Beyond 500 mg/L of dissolved solids, the palatability of water in drinking decreases and may cause gastro intestinal irritation¹³. Thus, the observations indicate that people of western part of the district may have some gastro intestinal problems related with drinking waters.

Chloride :

The chloride concentration variation in the district in open wells and hand pump water samples show that in most of the open well samples chloride is within 100 mg/L, except some pockets where it goes up to 200 mg/L. It shows that the water is mostly satisfactory for the domestic use.

Sulfate :

It appears that most of the open wells in eastern half portion of the district are having sulfate concentration below 48 mg/L, whereas towards western side, it goes up to 96 mg/L. In the hand pump samples, the trend is almost reverse. Observations indicate that in western areas of the district the sulfate concentration is mostly below 48 mg/L, whereas in eastern part of the district, it goes beyond 48 mg/L and reach up to 96 mg/L. This may be possibly due to sulfate salt bearing geological strata in the area at deeper levels.

Nitrate :

The analysis of nitrate concentration in water samples obtained from open wells and hand pumps reveals that waters of open wells near villages Khariaon, Harhuan and Sindhora in the north, Chiraigaon in the east and Khardupur in the west have nitrate concentrations above

45 mg NO₃⁻/L. Similarly, water from hand pumps near village Shivpur shows nitrate concentrations beyond 45 mg NO₃⁻/L, which is the desirable and upper permissible limit for nitrate concentration in water for drinking purpose. A closer analysis about the nitrate concentration suggests that barring some central zone of the district, the nitrate concentration in almost whole of the district is beyond 22.5 mg NO₃⁻/L, and below 45 mg NO₃⁻/L. A water having nitrate concentration below 22.5 mg NO₃⁻/L, is said to be safe for agricultural uses, but higher than 22.5 mg NO₃⁻/L shows increasing problems¹⁵. Thus, water from both open wells as well as tube wells appear to have gone in the increasing problem zone for agricultural purposes with regard to nitrate concentrations. This is possibly due to unrestricted use of nitrogenous fertilizers in agricultural practices in the district.

Conclusions :

Nitrate contamination of ground water has become a major challenge to the environmentalist in the developing countries. The city of Varanasi withdraws a significant amount of drinking water from ground water sources. Therefore, the present study has attempted to identify the area affected by nitrate contamination in ground water of Varanasi district. CPCB¹⁶ has prepared a report giving status of ground water quality in various cities of India, including Varanasi. The present study has focused more on sub urban and rural areas of the Varanasi district in order to supplement the data base in this direction.

Within the limits of sampling and examinations, following conclusions can be drawn from the present study :

- (i) Nitrate concentrations in the ground waters of the sub urban and fringe rural areas around Varanasi city appear to have reached levels which need close monitoring.
- (ii) Nitrate concentrations are more than 22.5 mg NO₃⁻/L in open wells as well as hand pumps drawn water from a large portion of the district, putting them in the “increasing problem” zone for agricultural uses.
- (iii) Nitrate concentration is beyond desirable and permissible limits for drinking purpose in the open well waters around villages Khariaon, Harhuan and Sindhora in the north, Chiraigaon in the east, Shivpur in the south and Khardupur in the west.

- (iv) Alkalinity and dissolved solids in both open well and hand pump waters appear to have exceeded the desirable limits for drinking, although are still within permissible limits in major parts of the sub urban and rural areas of Varanasi district.
- (v) The sites which show higher concentrations of nitrate should be monitored regularly and the source of nitrate leaching to ground waters should be identified for control strategies.
- (vi) All areas showing turbidity levels beyond 5 NTU should be monitored for iron content in the water, because they may be correlated.

Experimental

Sampling of ground water and their analysis :

Locations of different ground water sampling points were obtained using Global Positioning System (GPS).

GPS locations and water table depth of sampling locations :

Total 45 samples were collected from various locations. Out of which, 30 sampling sites were from open wells and 15 from hand pumps around Varanasi district.

GPS locations, name and approximate depths of ground water table (in meter) of sampling sites are given in Table 3 (open wells) and Table 4 (hand pumps).

Sl. no.	Latitude	Longitude	Name of place/ village	Approximate depth (m)
1.	25.24674	82.97478	Nuawan	9.24
2.	25.22967	82.93439	Barchawam	3.00
3.	25.20642	82.90144	Rudauli	4.10
4.	25.17564	82.87753	Adalpura	16.80
5.	25.19849	82.84008	Jakhni	11.10
6.	25.23475	82.84399	Koili	13.20
7.	25.26134	82.84427	Rajatalab	11.40
8.	25.28472	82.79994	Mirzaurad	9.30
9.	25.28471	82.77990	Chitrasenpur	12.20
10.	25.27598	82.71170	Kapsethi	7.80
11.	25.37124	82.92271	Harahua	18.30
12.	25.37648	82.91465	Jamalpur	12.00
13.	25.42112	82.87640	Kuhar	8.70
14.	25.51879	82.81239	Kaharion	18.00
15.	25.55585	82.79366	Dabhatua	7.80
16.	25.50505	82.80945	Dabhtua	3.00

Table-3 (contd.)

17.	25.5141	82.76165	Kuar	24.00
18.	25.48322	82.76726	Devchandpur	4.80
19.	25.45367	82.78248	Bdaghaon	6.60
20.	25.42992	82.81140	Kundi	17.40
21.	25.39756	82.77973	Kalikadham	7.50
22.	25.37998	82.57301	Kharadu	12.30
23.	25.36296	82.97509	Chandmari	8.94
24.	25.42281	82.96341	Plahaipatti	12.00
25.	25.48533	82.94168	Sindhora	6.93
26.	25.5323	82.93290	Jewar	13.44
27.	25.45922	82.98880	Hariadih	16.40
28.	25.44339	83.09360	Narayanpur	18.00
29.	25.37848	83.05367	Chiraigaon	27.00
30.	25.36546	83.05973	Jhulupur	6.60

Table 4. Hand pump sampling locations

Sl. no.	Latitude	Longitude	Name of place/ village	Approximate depth (m)
1.	25.18468	82.84847	Shansapur	57.00
2.	25.26892	82.71043	Thatra	24.00
3.	25.35441	82.73563	Baruka	54.00
4.	25.32329	82.82591	Karuna	50.00
5.	25.31881	82.85932	Lohta	39.00
6.	25.31334	82.94966	Newada	17.00
7.	25.28396	82.97138	DLW	17.00
8.	25.28912	82.96056	Shivpur	48.00
9.	25.35429	82.96453	Bhel	18.30
10.	25.46082	82.83903	Phulpur	4.80
11.	25.35904	82.80979	Bashai	18.00
12.	25.38856	82.96667	Auron	21.00
13.	25.45987	82.95417	Gurthama Bazar	45.00
14.	25.41409	83.77990	Sandaha	9.90
15.	25.38479	83.11835	Lahartara	36.00

Analysis of nitrate and other parameters :

All the parameters were determined as per the Standard Method¹⁷.

Nitrate was measured by Ion Selective Electrode (ISE) method using digital Ion-pH meter (HANNA HI 4222) of Hanna Equipments (India) Pvt. Ltd., Navi Mumbai, India.

A known volume (10–25 mL) of the sample was taken in a beaker (100 mL size) and equal volume of TISAB (Total Ionic Strength Adjustment Buffer) solution was added to each sample and stirred with a magnetic stirrer

for one minute. The electrode tip was immersed in the sample and reading was recorded when stable. A pre-calibration of instrument with known solutions of nitrate standards is required for sample analysis.

Similarly, the pH and turbidity of the samples were also measured by electrode method. The instruments were calibrated first with known standard solutions and after that reading were noted directly to dip the electrode tip in water samples.

Total dissolved solid (TDS) was determined by Conductivity-TDS meter (Systronics India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India).

Titrimetric methods were used to determine dissolved oxygen (DO) (Iodometric method), chloride (Argentometric method) and alkalinity in collected ground water samples.

Nephelometric (Turbidity) method was used to determine the sulfate in the samples. At first, Nephelometer was calibrated with the known strength of turbidity solutions. A calibration curve was plotted in between Nephelometric turbidity unit (NTU) of standards vs concentrations of standard sulfate solution. The readings of sulfate in samples were obtained from the graph.

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